

Social Commerce : Investigating Impact of Social Media on Consumer Buying Behavior

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Abstract : *The dynamic evolution of social media and internet networking has significantly transformed consumer behavior, reshaping contemporary marketing strategies. This shift, driven by the rise of social commerce, amplifies social media's influence in the digital marketing sphere. Our investigation delves into the profound impact of these platforms on shaping purchasing decisions and emphasizes the crucial role of understanding consumer demographics in strategic planning. Furthermore, this comprehensive study scrutinizes the influence of user generated content on consumer trust, a vital factor in the evolving realm of social commerce. Employing a data-driven methodology and questionnaires, the study analyzes consumer demographics, purchasing patterns, engagement, and involvement in social commerce. The findings enhance understanding for businesses aiming to optimize their social commerce strategies and adapt to evolving consumer landscapes. These insights are valuable for marketers, policymakers, researchers, and consumers, offering a deeper comprehension of social commerce.*

Keywords : Social Commerce, Consumer Behavior, Social Media, User-generated Content, Trust, Challenges, Engagement, Purchasing Decisions.

INTRODUCTION:

Social media's ever-changing viewpoint has fundamentally changed how people engage, communicate, and make decisions about what to buy in today's linked society. The word "Social Commerce," which skillfully blends social media and online buying to enable firms in influencing customer choices, has emerged as a result of this revolutionary shift and driving economic growth (Abaid Ullah

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Zafar, 2019). Certainly, social media exerts a noteworthy influence on consumer behavior. People are progressively turning to these platforms to uncover products, gather suggestions from peers, and narrate their own encounters. These social media channels have transformed into digital marketplaces featuring an extensive and varied group of users. These users play an active role in shaping their purchasing choices and engaging with brands. E-commerce has distinctly molded the business environment, bringing forth seven effective online business frameworks that cater to different market sectors. These models encompass B2C, B2B, C2C, D2C, C2B, B2A, and C2A, addressing a wide array of customer interactions and transactions. (Nitu Sharma, 2023). These frameworks enable online transactions and fundamentally transform the methods through which products and services are both presented and acquired.

A study conducted by (Zaryab Sheikh, 2019) reveals that a considerable portion of digital consumers, approximately 67%, favor suggestions from the virtual community, and a notable 83% of online buyers are eager to share information about their purchases with friends. Additionally, research carried out by (Faradewi Bee A.Rahman, 2023) underscores how social commerce not only revolutionizes a firm's activities but also has a substantial impact on consumer actions within the domain of online shopping encounters.

In addition, social commerce brings the convenience of immediate online purchases to consumers, granting them the ability to acquire products and services that may not be locally available, at their preferred time, as highlighted by (Faradewi Bee A.Rahman, 2023). This level of accessibility has revolutionized the way businesses promote their offerings. Nowadays, companies harness social media platforms to connect with a wider audience, interact with customers, and establish a more robust brand presence. Interactive content, collaborations with influencers, and contributions from users are employed to attract and retain shoppers, cultivating a feeling of community akin to brand communities. In today's digital era, social media assumes a pivotal role, as influencers, friends, and family exert significant influence over consumer inclinations. Social validation and positive appraisals on these platforms wield a profound impact on purchase choices.

As outlined by (Hajli, 2017), Customers use their social media profiles to help them make well-informed decisions when they shop. Social media platforms include features such as the "Like" button on Facebook, the "Tweet" option on Twitter, and the "Share" feature on Plurk, which allow users to quickly share commercial content with their social network. The sharing process mostly focuses

on friends exchanging insights on social media sites, rather than offering conventional feedback to anonymous online shoppers, as elucidated by (Ting-Peng Liang, 2011). Studies demonstrate that consumers actively participate in social commerce (s-commerce) with the intention of enhancing their shopping efficiency, as indicated by research conducted by (Kim, 2013; Liang, Ho, Li, & Turban, 2011; Liang T. a., 2011). They capitalize on a range of advantages, including convenience, social endorsements, personalized experiences, immediate access to information, seamless checkout processes, real-time customer assistance, time-limited promotions, and enticing deals, along with the contagious nature of social sharing. By harnessing these elements, consumers strive to make more informed and improved purchasing choices when utilizing social commerce platforms, as highlighted by (Xi Hu, 2019).

Due to the widespread popularity of social commerce, numerous websites catering to a large user base have arisen, as mentioned in the work of (Tredinnick, 2006). Nonetheless, social commerce still grapples with several design challenges. A notable challenge stems from the two distinct paths along which social commerce is evolving, leading to the emergence of two distinct categories of social commerce applications. The first category integrates e-commerce functionalities into social networking websites, while the second category embeds social networking features into e-commerce websites, as discussed by (Curty, 2011).

Recent years have witnessed a rapid surge in the growth of social commerce, attributed to the important impact that user engagement—a key component of social media applications—has for organizations. For instance, the case of Threadless.com illustrates how involving users in submitting T-shirt design concepts through an online community effectively drives product development, identifies emerging market trends, and bolsters sales, as highlighted by (Benyoucef, 2013). The objective of this study is to have a thorough understanding of the functioning of social commerce through the alignment of company objectives with social media platform. To achieve this, the study investigates how the perceived characteristics of social vendors influence trust and social commerce. Additionally, it delves into how users perceive platform utilization and the presence of other users, as explored by (Yahia, 2018).

A key distinction between e-commerce and social commerce lies in how users are perceived and engaged. In traditional e-commerce, users are often seen as isolated individuals, disconnected from their communities, and acting independently. The flow of information is mostly one-way, with businesses conveying messages to users, and little opportunity for users to provide feedback

to the platform (Benyoucef Z. H., 2013). On the flip side, within the realm of social commerce, the interaction between users and the platform is perceived as a collaborative process driven by the community. Users and prospective users participate in online commerce services and applications as active members of a larger community. This engagement enables users to express their preferences and endorse products within their networks, potentially impacting the buying choices and actions of fellow community members, as elucidated by (Huang, 2013).

In a comprehensive overview, this research is committed to shedding light on the transformative impact of social commerce on consumer behavior, profoundly reshaping the traditional shopping landscape. This paradigm shift seamlessly grants individuals access to an extensive spectrum of products and services via online platforms. Additionally, businesses strategically harness the power of social media to establish meaningful connections, elevate user experiences, and provide enhanced value. A salient trend emerging is the increasing reliance of consumers on social media for peer-endorsed product insights and feedback, significantly shaping their purchasing choices. This trend highlights social commerce's changing role in consumer decision-making, and investigating it is a primary area of interest. The emergence of social commerce, a multitude of advantages are introduced, including the convenience of personalized recommendations, real-time support, and empowerment for consumers to make well-informed decisions. While the rise of social commerce has led to the emergence of numerous online platforms, it concurrently presents design challenges due to its multifaceted evolution. However, the burgeoning influence of user engagement within social commerce has proven to be a boon for businesses, fostering innovation, imparting profound market insights, and propelling increased sales. The primary objective of this research is to align business strategies with social media tactics, delving into the ways perceived vendor traits influence trust and social commerce. Additionally, the study underscores the pivotal role of interactions that facilitate the exchange of preferences and recommendations among users.

This comprehensive exploration aims to provide a holistic understanding of the intricate relationships between different social media platforms, user-generated content, social media platform features, and consumer buying behavior. This research contributes significant insights to a diverse range of stakeholders. For market researchers, it provides a nuanced understanding of how social commerce dynamics impact consumer behavior, enabling them to refine their methodologies and generate more accurate insights. Business leaders

stand to gain actionable insights into effectively leveraging social commerce strategies, optimizing customer engagement, and navigating challenges in this evolving landscape. Moreover, policymakers and industry regulators can benefit from an informed perspective on how social commerce is reshaping consumer interactions and transactions. Ultimately, this study not only navigates the paradigm shift brought by social commerce but also endeavors to provide empirical insights into the multifaceted interplay of these variables, thereby making a substantial contribution to the realm of consumer behavior, market research practices, and the evolving business landscape at large.

Review of Literature :

Panpan Wang, Qian Huang (2023) Their research reveals digital influencers enhance social commerce. Information and expertise are digital influencers' social powers. Both powers affect client participation. Interactions impact social commerce purchases. A survey reveals digital influencer-based businesses leverage social commerce to boost consumer engagement and revenue.

Pejman Ebrahimi, et al, (2023) In their study, Strategic social networking characteristics alter online customer purchase behavior, according to authors. The key variables for ISM methodology and experts are "consumer engagement," "value perception," and "risk perception." Also stressed: "Trust," "Social influence," "Social support," and "Value co-creation". Platforms employ analytics to engage users and inform purchases. This data can be used to develop new social networking user engagement concepts or study variable correlations.

Ahmad Samed Al-Adwana, Husam Yaseen, et al, (2023) Their research, E-commerce and social media lessen product uncertainty. Data quality, seller reputation, and positive product uncertainty evaluations are assessed. These attributes reduce vendor uncertainty, per 471 consumer reviews. These features and social commerce consumers' product uncertainty perceptions are mediated by seller uncertainty. Their research impacts social commerce uncertainty theory and practice.

Jian Wang, et al, (2022) This study examines social commerce purchasing intent and trust. The study of 19 studies found that trust increases customers' buying intentions. Trust in sellers influences consumers' purchasing intentions more than other believe objects, and these consumers trust forums and communities more. The data show that trust-building tactics increase social commerce client loyalty and engagement.

Abaid Ullah Zafar, et al, (2019). In their research, The authors analyze how social media influencers and interactive features affect social commerce and impulsive buying. They examine how celebrity posts affect 452 Pakistani Facebook users' sincerity, contradicting views, observation, and impulsive buying. These traits greatly reduce impulsive spending and most relationships except negative emotions. Their research on social commerce and impulse buying offers theoretical and managerial insights into consumer behaviour.

Xi Hu, et al, (2019) In this paper, Interactivity and social media influencers affect social commerce impulsive buying, according to the study. They examined 452 Facebook Pakistanis. According to the study, celebrity posts affect genuineness, competing ideas, observation, and impulsive buy. Except for negative emotions and reckless expenditure, these elements regulate most associations. This study examines social commerce and impulsive buying theoretically and managerially.

Objectives :

1. To examine the extent to which social media platforms influence consumer buying behavior.
2. To identify the key factors that drive the consumers to engage in social commerce activities.

Research Methodology :

In this research, a rigorous and systematic methodology is employed to examine how social media affects customer buying behavior in social commerce. A quantitative approach is adopted, with data collected through structured survey questionnaires distributed to a diverse sample of consumers actively engaged in customer buying patterns.

The sampling technique used for participant selection ensures that the sample is representative and diverse, comprising individuals from different demographics. Data analysis techniques, such as regression analysis and correlation analysis, are applied to test the hypotheses formulated for this study.

Descriptive statistics, including mean, median, and standard deviation, are calculated to summarize and describe the main characteristics of the collected data. The data analysis results are interpreted to derive significant implications about the impact of media on consumer purchasing behavior, as well as the influence of user-generated content and social media platform features on customer trust and purchase decisions within the context of social commerce.

The study admits sample size and data gathering techniques, which may restrict generalizability. Despite these constraints, the study tries to illuminate the dynamic relationship between social media, consumer behaviour, and social commerce.

Based on the research findings, the study will offer recommendations to businesses, marketers, and social media platforms to optimize their social commerce strategies and enhance customer engagement approaches. The study's findings, contributes to the body of knowledge on social commerce and consumer behavior. The research outcomes hold potential implications for businesses and stakeholders seeking to capitalize on the opportunities presented by the evolving digital marketplace

Statement of Problem :

Social commerce is a concept that has emerged in the modern business environment as a result of the combination of social media and consumer behaviour. But the complex interaction between social media and consumer purchasing patterns continues to be a riddle with many layers. The main issue this study attempts to solve is the need to determine how much influence social media platforms have over customer preferences and purchase behaviour. This analysis goes further to pinpoint the crucial elements that encourage customers into engaging in social commerce activities. The study also intends to analyse how user-content affects customer trust and decision-making in the context of social commerce. In addition, it aims to investigate how consumers view products, which in turn affects how actively they engage in social commerce. This research aims to clarify the intricacies of social commerce, providing crucial insights for firms and marketers navigating this changing environment as the digital revolution redefines the dynamics of customer purchase intentions.

Significance of the Study :

This study has significant implications for business due to the social commerce industry's changing environment. To improve their digital marketing approach, firms must understand how social media affects customer buying behavior. The findings of this study can help organizations allocate resources among social media channels to engage potential customers more effectively.

To create more personalized and engaging online experiences, businesses must first identify the major drivers of social commerce activity participation. Businesses should tailor their client interactions to these factors to build stronger relationships and encourage social commerce involvement.

In conclusion, this study helps organizations make strategic decisions by revealing the complex interaction between social media and customer behavior in social commerce. The study may impact corporate strategies, marketing efficacy, and the scholarly debate on digital commerce's evolution.

Scope of the Study :

The purpose of this research is to analyse, in as much depth as possible, how the influence of social media on consumer buying habits connects to the field of social commerce. This entails investigating various social media networks, determining the important characteristics that drive customer engagement. The research was conducted with the intention of providing a nuanced understanding of the complex processes that shape consumer behaviours in social commerce. The research aimed to encompass a broad spectrum of geographic regions and demographic groups.

Research Variables and Conceptual Framework :

Source: primary

Hypotheses Formation:

This study formulates and tests hypotheses to understand the complex interaction between social media platforms, consumer purchasing behavior, personality factors, and social media involvement. A comprehensive literature assessment yields two possibilities for investigation:

Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : Social media platforms have no significant impact on consumer purchasing behavior.

H_{01a} : Social media platforms have a significant impact on consumer purchasing behavior.

Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no relationship between social media engagement and consumer buying decisions.

H_{02a} : There is a positive relationship between social media engagement and consumer buying decisions.

Hypothesis 3

H_{03} : No correlation exists between consumer demographics and their participation in social commerce.

H_{03a} : Consumer demographics are related to their engagement in social commerce activities.

Data Analysis :

H_{01} : Social media platforms have no significant impact on consumer Buying behavior.

H_{01a} : Social media platforms have a significant impact on consumer Buying behavior.

Social Media Impact on Consumer Purchasing : Regression Analysis

Table 1(a): Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.684	0.467	0.463	0.722
<i>Source: Primary</i>				

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Platforms

Table 1(b): ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	58.517	1	58.517	112.273	.000
	Residual	66.714	128	0.521		
	Total	125.231	129			
<i>Source: Primary</i>						

Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Platforms

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behavior

Table 1(c): Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.757	0.228		3.320	0.00
	Social Media Platforms	0.743	0.070	0.684	10.60	.000
<i>Source: Primary</i>						

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behavior

Interpretation:

X-axis- Independent variable = social media platforms.

Y-axis Dependent variable = consumer buying behavior.

The regression study in Table-1(a) shows that social media platforms explain 46.7% of customer purchase behavior. The regression analysis revealed a

significant positive correlation between social media platforms and consumer buying behavior (coefficient = 0.743, $F(1,130) = 112.273$, $p < 0.05$), supporting alternative hypotheses. The R square value of 0.467 from Table 1(a) shows that social media platforms (independent variable) affect customer buying behavior (dependent variable) by 46.75. A positive correlation exists between social media platforms and customer buying behavior ($R = 0.743$, $F(1,130) = 112.273$, $p < 0.05$).

According to Table-1(c), the regression constant was 0.757. The regression coefficients show a 0.743 unit change in consumer buying behavior for every unit change in social media ($p < 0.05$). The regression slope line, $Y = a + Bx$, where $a = 0.757$, $B = 0.743$, $X =$ Social Media Platforms and $Y =$ Consumer Buying Behavior, shows that as the value of X (social media platforms) increases by 1, the value of Y (consumer buying behavior) increases by 0.743.

Hypotheses 2:

H_{02} : There is no relationship between social media engagement and consumer buying decisions.

H_{02a} : There is a positive relationship between social media engagement and consumer buying decisions.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis between Social Media Engagement and Consumer Buying Decisions			
		Social Media Engagement	Consumer Buying Decisions
Social Media Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	0.554
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	N	130	130
Consumer Buying Decisions	Pearson Correlation	0.554	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	130	130
<i>Source: Primary</i>			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 2: Relationship Visualization between Social Media Engagement and Consumer Buying Decisions

Source: Primary

Interpretation:

According to Table-2, social media increases consumer expenditure by 0.554. Specific social media purchases rise. Consumer purchase decisions are increased by social media use, since both correlations had 0.00 p-values (Sig. 2-tailed). Previous research has shown that social media greatly influences customer purchases (Zirena-Bejarano, 2023; Dhar, J., & Jha, A. K. (2014); Barhemmati & Ahmad, 2015). In 2023, Zirena-Bejarano found social media greatly influenced purchases. Researchers found that social media makes product reviews, testimonials, and peer input accessible. Peer-reviewed information drives current buying, therefore social media is vital. According to Dhar & Jha (2014), social media affects purchases. According to our analysis, social media influences customer purchases. Sales rise with consumer interaction, say Barhemmati & Ahmad (2015). (2017) Zhang et al. observed social media boosts shopping. Social media substantially influences client purchasing. Studies suggest that social media influences client selections, making it vital to marketing.

Stats disprove H_{01} that social media does not effect consumer purchase behavior. We promote H_{01a} .

Figure-2 displays this link using a marker data scatter plot. Purchases are positively and modestly correlated with social media activity. Sales increase with social media, as shown by the growing Y-axis.

Objective 2 : To identify the key factors that drive consumers to engage in social commerce activities.

H₀₃ : No correlation exists between consumer demographics and their participation in social commerce.

H_{03a} : Consumer demographics are related to their engagement in social commerce activities.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis between Consumer Demographics and Consumer Buying Behavior in Social Commerce			
		Consumer Demographics	Consumer Buying Behavior
Consumer Demographics	Pearson Correlation	1.00	0.47
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00
	N	130	130
Consumer Buying Behavior	Pearson Correlation	0.47	1.00
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	
	N	130	130
<i>Source: Primary</i>			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation:

Consumer demographics positively correlate with purchase behavior by 0.47 in Table 3. Consumer qualities moderately affect purchase decisions, as evidenced by the statistically significant p-value (sig. 2 tailed) of 0.00. The results reveal that demographics greatly influence consumer purchasing behavior. Demographics like age, wealth, geography, and others may influence client purchases. The statistically significant p-value and moderate correlation coefficient of 0.47 suggest a substantial connection.

Figure-3 : Visualization of the Relationship between Consumer Demographics and Consumer Buying Behavior in Social Commerce

Social commerce participation depends on user demographics (Colicev, Kumar, & O'Connor, 2019). This emphasizes consumer qualities and social commerce.

The scatter plot in Figure 3 reveals a moderate positive association between demographics and buying behavior. Consumer purchase decisions grow as demographics improve, as shown by the trend line's increased slope along the X-axis. Demographics influence consumer buying decisions on the Y-axis. This graph illustrates the relationship's strength and direction beyond statistical data. In Conclusion, **we accept the alternative hypothesis (H1), indicating that consumer demographics are related to their engagement in social commerce activities. The null hypothesis (H0), which stated no correlation exists, is rejected based on the findings from this analysis.**

Practical Implications:

This study has major ramifications for social commerce businesses. It emphasizes user-centric platform design for engagement and happiness. Marketing efficacy can be improved by demographically targeting content. Adaptability is essential in the ever-changing social media landscape. These implications help businesses engage users and succeed in social commerce.

Managerial Implications and Conclusion :

In conclusion, Social commerce platform study shows that platforms, user attributes, and dynamic settings strongly influence consumer behavior. The

association between customer demographics and buying behavior and the positive correlation between social media involvement and consumer purchase decisions show how important user attributes are. The widespread assumption is that demographics are crucial to understanding consumer behavior. These findings suggest that social commerce requires constant change and a user-centric approach. Social commerce systems should monitor social media changes because they influence consumer behavior. However, these findings are context-specific and may not apply in all cases. The study emphasises longitudinal research to capture changing trends in social commerce, which is dynamic.

Our research suggests a flexible and nuanced approach to understanding social commerce's intricate interaction across platforms, user attributes, and changing environments. In "The Only Constant in Life Is Change," Mutambara (2022) correctly stated that social commerce requires constant change and a deep understanding of user dynamics.

Limitations and Future Directions:

Survey data and demographic focus may restrict generalizability of this study. Dynamic digital landscape may alter findings over time. Future studies may explore several techniques to overcome these issues and make a significant contribution to the subject. Longitudinal studies of user behavior and platform dynamics would help scholars understand how social commerce is changing. To make the study more thorough, the demographic range must be increased. Using objective behavior data and survey data could reveal user engagement. Exploring how AR and VR effect social commerce might create new fields of study. Social commerce privacy and data security raise ethical concerns. This will clarify how these issues effect user trust and engagement. Comparing social commerce platforms or social commerce and traditional e-commerce may reveal unique user behavior and preferences. These guidelines outline future social commerce research, which is expanding.

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